

Artificial intelligence for sex and gender analysis in evidence synthesis – potential opportunities and challenges: Protocol for a survey study

Diana Buitrago-Garcia^{1*}, Jesús López-Alcalde^{1,2,3*}, Anna Katharina Tietjen¹, Claudia Canella¹, Janna Hastings⁴, Claudia M. Witt¹

¹ Complementary and Integrative Digital Health, Institute of Primary Care, University of Zurich and University Hospital Zurich, Switzerland

² Faculty of Medicine, Universidad Francisco de Vitoria (UFV), Madrid, Spain

³ Instituto Ramón y Cajal de Investigación Sanitaria (IRYCIS), Unidad de bioestadística clínica, Hospital Universitario Ramón y Cajal, (CIBERESP), Cochrane Madrid, Madrid, Spain

⁴ Idiap Research Institute, Martigny, Switzerland

* Both contributed equally as first authors

Contact person:

Jesús López-Alcalde

Jesus.lopez@usz.ch

University Hospital Zurich, Institute for Complementary and Integrative Medicine

Sonneggstrasse 6, 8091 Zurich, Switzerland

Phone +41 44 255 51 38

Date protocol completed: 7 April 2026

Signature: Jesús López Alcalde

1 Introduction

This survey will inform the project: [Artificial Intelligence to Expedite Sex/Gender Analysis in Evidence Synthesis: a use case of Digital Health Interventions for Cancer Patients](#)¹. This is a three-year project funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) under the National Research Programme (NRP) 83 “Gender Medicine and Health (project number 408340_227036)”². The general aim of this survey is to explore how artificial intelligence (AI) can be applied to enhance the integration of sex and gender considerations in evidence synthesis.

2 Survey objectives

Objective 1. To identify opportunities for AI to accelerate and improve the consideration of sex and gender in evidence synthesis

Objective 2. To identify challenges associated with using AI to support the integration of sex and gender in evidence synthesis.

Objective 3. To identify key considerations for developing prompts that address sex and gender in evidence synthesis.

3 Methods

3.1 Study design

We will conduct a web-based survey in English using convenience sampling, targeting individuals involved in evidence synthesis in the last five years. Participation will be voluntary, and the survey will be anonymous. To maintain anonymity, only general personal information will be collected, such as gender identity and geographic region (Europe, Americas, Asia, Africa, Oceania). Informed consent will be obtained prior to initiating the survey. Participants may withdraw at any time.

The final survey manuscript will be reported according to the *Checklist for Reporting Results of Internet E-Surveys* reporting guideline (CHERRIES)³.

3.2 Inclusion criteria

Any person who has been involved in at least one evidence synthesis report over the last five years.

Evidence synthesis refers to a broad term referring to different types of reviews that systematically compile and analyse information from multiple documents, such as studies or reports on a similar topic, to develop an overall understanding of the results. Common forms of evidence syntheses include systematic reviews, rapid reviews, and scoping reviews⁴. Participants may be involved at any stage and type of evidence synthesis.

Participants may assume **any role within the evidence synthesis ecosystem**, as defined by the RAISE initiative⁵:

1. **Evidence synthesists:** Individuals involved in conducting evidence syntheses, including authors, information specialists, statisticians, and domain experts.
2. **Methodologists:** Individuals responsible for developing and evaluating methodological standards, including those involved in validation studies, guideline development, and AI-related research.
3. **AI tool developers:** Individuals who develop or implement AI tools to support evidence synthesis tasks.
4. **Organisations that produce evidence synthesis:** Entities responsible for establishing and implementing standards and policies for conducting and reporting evidence synthesis.
5. **Publishers of evidence synthesis:** Journal editors, peer reviewers, and organisations responsible for editorial processes or quality assurance.

3.3 Instrument development and design

Three researchers (DBG, JLA, and CW) developed the questionnaire based on similar surveys.^{6,7}, a narrative review of AI-related documents on evidence synthesis and own

expertise. These sources were reviewed by the survey team to ensure the questionnaire's relevance. The draft survey, prepared in MS Word, was subsequently reviewed by the project's advisory board, which included experts from various fields of evidence synthesis, to ensure comprehensiveness. Following revisions, the survey was designed using the *SoSci Survey tool* (Version 3.5.01)⁸. A pilot test was then conducted with researchers from the *Chair of Complementary and Integrative Digital Health* (Institute of Primary Care, University of Zurich and University Hospital Zurich) to assess the questions, tool functionality, and completion time.

3.3.1 Survey questions

The survey has 25 questions with 90 items, predominantly multiple-choice. It covers roles and experience in evidence synthesis over the past five years, users' experience incorporating sex and gender considerations in evidence synthesis, the use of AI in evidence synthesis and anticipated needs related to prompt development. Questions addressing challenges and opportunities associated with the use of AI to integrate sex and gender considerations are presented using Likert scales. The estimated completion time is 15 minutes. Participants may review and modify their responses and save their progress for later completion. Responses will not be mandatory; however, alerts will remind participants of unanswered questions. The survey employs adaptive questioning based on respondents' experience with AI in evidence synthesis and with sex/gender considerations. If participants are unsure about an item, we will offer the option to answer "not sure". Appendix 1 presents the survey.

3.3.2 Survey dissemination

Participants will be recruited through multiple channels, including social media (LinkedIn), professional networks, and direct contact with authors of evidence synthesis studies. A LinkedIn infographic will be used to promote participation. Detailed project information will be available on the project's website (<https://www.hausarztmedizin.uzh.ch/en/kidig.html>) and linked to the survey landing

page. We will compile a database of authors who have published evidence syntheses in the past five years using the Web of Science database and send invitations to complete the survey via email. Invitations will also be sent to relevant organisations and professional contacts. No incentives to participate will be provided. The survey will be open for a maximum of three months.

3.3.3 Survey administration

The survey will be accessed via a web link directing participants to the SoSci Survey platform. The link will be distributed via email invitations, social media posts, and the project-related website.

3.4 Data analysis and presentation

Statistical analysis will be performed using R software⁹. As this is an exploratory study, no formal sample size calculation will be performed.

The analysis for each survey item will include all respondents who provide consent for participation and report having contributed to at least one evidence synthesis report in the past five years.

The number of survey items answered per participant will not be an inclusion criterion. We will report the completeness rate, defined as the proportion of participants who met the inclusion criteria and completed all survey questions relevant to their profile. We will also report the completion rate, defined as the proportion of participants who met the inclusion criteria and submitted the final survey question (region).

We will analyse data only for participants whose responses are known, using the total number of participants with data recorded for the item as the denominator. Thus, we will not apply imputation methods for missing data. For Likert-scale items, responses of “I am not sure” and missing responses will not be included in the analysis. We will report the proportions of missing and “I am not sure” responses for each item.

We will use descriptive statistics (percentages, means and standard deviations (SDs), and medians and interquartile ranges (IQRs)) to summarise dichotomous and quantitative data in narrative and tabular formats.

We plan to explore associations between opportunities and challenges and the following factors:

- Experience using AI for evidence synthesis: “Yes” vs “No”
- Experience incorporating sex and gender considerations in evidence synthesis: “Yes” vs “No”
- Experience using AI to perform sex- or gender-related tasks in evidence synthesis: “Yes” vs “No”
- Geographical region: Europe, Americas, Oceania, Asia, Africa
- Gender identity: Women vs Men vs Other (Non-binary, gender diverse, other or “I prefer not to answer”)
- Experience in evidence synthesis: 1-2 vs 3-10 vs 11 or more evidence syntheses conducted in the past five years

As part of the exploratory analysis, associations will be examined using the Pearson chi-squared test¹⁰ or Fisher’s exact test¹¹, as appropriate. If necessary, due to small samples, responses will be grouped into two categories. The impact of the pooling of categories on the results will be assessed through sensitivity analyses that retain the original category classification.

For open-text questions, we will conduct a qualitative thematic analysis to group participants' comments into overarching categories¹², identifying key aspects needed for AI to support the integration of sex and gender in evidence synthesis. The software MAXQDA 24 (Release 24.11.0) will be used to perform the analyses.

4 Acknowledgements

Casey Murphy for improving the clarity and style of the protocol.

5 Funding

This survey is part of the research project “Artificial Intelligence (AI) to Expedite Sex/Gender Analysis in Evidence Synthesis: A Use Case of Digital Health Interventions for Cancer Patients.” This three-year project (2025–2027) is funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) under the NRP 83 – Gender Medicine and Health program (grant no. 408340_227036).

6 Ethics

The Cantonal Ethics Committee Zurich stated that the project did not fall within the scope of the Human Research Act in Switzerland (BASEC-Nr Req-2024-00971; July 26, 2024).

7 Declarations

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

8 Author contributions

JLA, CW and JH conceived the study. DBG, JLA and CW designed the questionnaire. DBG and JLA wrote the first draft of this protocol. All authors read the protocol critically and approved its final version. CW, JLA and JH obtained funding for this survey. AKT implemented the survey in SoSci Survey. CW is the guarantor.

9 State of the survey process at the time of registration

Step	Description	Status
1. Draft survey questionnaire	The questionnaire was developed by DBG, JLA, and CW, using prior surveys and a narrative review.	Completed
2. Survey refinement	The draft was reviewed by the project's advisory board for comprehensiveness and relevance.	Completed
3. Survey tool setup	The survey was set up using SoSci Survey (Version 3.5.01).	Completed
4. Survey pilot testing	A pilot test was conducted with researchers at the University of Zurich and University Hospital Zurich.	Completed
5. Survey launch	The survey was launched via a web link distributed through multiple channels.	Completed
6. Participants' recruitment	Participants were recruited through social media, professional networks, and direct author contact.	Ongoing
7. Data Collection	Data will be collected from survey respondents over at least a two-month period.	Ongoing
8. Data Analysis	Statistical analysis using R software. Descriptive statistics will summarise the results. A thematic analysis will be performed for open-text responses.	Upcoming
9. Reporting	Results will be reported following CHERRIES guidelines	Upcoming

10 References

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Appendix 1. Survey

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Opportunities and challenges for the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to consider sex and gender in evidence synthesis: survey study

This survey aims to gather views from **individuals involved in evidence synthesis² projects**. It explores the opportunities and challenges of applying **Artificial Intelligence (AI)²** to consider sex and gender in evidence synthesis.

**Some words accompanied by a question mark² contain concepts*

Who can participate?

Any person who has participated in **at least one evidence synthesis project in the last five years** (such as quantitative or qualitative evidence syntheses, meta-analyses or scoping reviews). This includes individuals involved in study selection, data extraction, or risk-of-bias assessment, as well as methodological specialists (e.g., information specialists or statisticians) and domain experts (e.g., clinicians, patients, or other stakeholders), among others.

Why participate in this survey?

Sex and gender are often overlooked or inadequately addressed in evidence synthesis, despite their impact on the frequency, severity, and treatment outcomes of various health conditions. For example, in a random sample of 38 Cochrane reviews on cardiovascular health, the terms "sex" and "gender" were often used interchangeably (PMID: 20384450). Similarly, only 3% of 113 Cochrane reviews on interventions to prevent hospital-acquired infections incorporated sex or gender related findings in their conclusions (PMID: 30876452).

The results of this survey will inform the development of a framework for using AI² to promote more inclusive evidence synthesis.

What is your contribution?

Your participation is voluntary and anonymous, that is, no identifiable information will be collected. The survey is expected to take less than **15 minutes**. You can save your answers and continue with the survey at any other time by clicking on the "Pause the survey" button.

Who are we?

This survey is part of the research project "Artificial Intelligence (AI) to Expedite Sex/Gender Analysis in Evidence Synthesis: A Use Case of Digital Health Interventions for Cancer Patients." This three-year project (2025–2027) is funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation under the NRP 83 – Gender Medicine and Health program (grant no. 408340_2270386/1): [AI to promote sex/gender in evidence synthesis](#)

If you have any questions, please contact us at survey@usz.ch

Project team

Study coordinator

Diana Buitrago-García

Cochrane Complementary Medicine Satellite Switzerland
Complementary and Integrative Digital Health Institute of Primary Care – University of Zurich and University Hospital Zurich, Zurich, Switzerland

Project Leaders

Claudia M. Witt and Jesús López-Alcalde

Cochrane Complementary Medicine Satellite Switzerland
Complementary and Integrative Digital Health Institute of Primary Care – University of Zurich and University Hospital Zurich, Zurich, Switzerland

Janna Hastings

IDIA Research Institute, Martigny, Switzerland.

[AI to Expedite Sex/Gender-Based Analysis in Evidence Synthesis | Primary Care at University of Zurich | UZH](#)

Consent to participate in the survey

I have read and understood the information above. I confirm that I have participated in at least one evidence synthesis project in the last five years. I volunteer to participate in the survey:

- Yes
 No

Next

Pause the survey

Section I. Experience in evidence synthesis in the last five years

1. What has been your role in evidence synthesis over the last five years?

Evidence synthesis involves reviewing the best available research using systematic and transparent methods. Examples are systematic reviews or scoping reviews ([RAISE 1 – recommendations v.2](#)).

Select all that apply

- Person working on evidence synthesis, such as systematic reviewer implementing study selection or data extraction
- Information specialist
- Statistician
- Qualitative researcher
- Domain expert: person with expertise in the review's topic
- Domain expert: person affected by the condition addressed in the review (patient or relative)
- Another role. Please specify:

2. In which evidence synthesis practices have you participated in the last five years?

Select all that apply

- Quantitative systematic reviews / Meta-analyses
- Qualitative evidence syntheses
- Systematic maps/Evidence (gap) maps / Scoping reviews / Overviews of reviews
- Mixed-methods systematic reviews, such as realist syntheses, mixed studies reviews, meta-summaries
- Scientometrics, bibliometrics
- Other evidence synthesis practice. Please specify:

3. Approximately, in how many evidence synthesis reports, such as systematic reviews or scoping reviews, have you participated in the last five years?

- 0
- 1-2
- 3-10
- 11-20
- 21 and more
- I have contributed to one or more evidence syntheses reports, though I do not remember the exact number

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Pause the survey

Section II. Experience in considering sex and gender in evidence synthesis

While sex refers to biological differences, gender incorporates the social roles associated with being male or female. Biological and gender-based differences between men and women result in differential health risks, disease incidence, and health service needs ([PMID: 24189691](#)).

4. Before this survey, were you aware of the difference between the concepts of sex and gender?

- Yes
- No
- I am not sure

5. Have you ever received any training or trained yourself on how to incorporate sex and gender considerations into evidence synthesis?

Select all that apply

- Short course (1 day or less)
- Longer course (more than 1 day)
- Supervision from experienced users
- Self-taught
- Other. Please specify:

I have no training at all: no courses, supervision or self-taught

6. Have you ever followed specific guidance for incorporating sex and gender considerations in any of your evidence syntheses?

Examples: Sex and Gender Equity in Research (SAGER) Guidelines, Cochrane Handbook, SGAT-SR, SGAT-SR2, PROGRESS-Plus, GRADE equity guidance, or PRO EDI

- Yes. Please specify:
- No
- Other. Please specify:
- I am not sure

7. Have you ever included sex and gender aspects in any of your evidence syntheses?

- Yes
- No
- I am not sure

9. Please feel free to share any additional thoughts, comments or observations.

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Section III. Using AI for evidence synthesis

10. Have you ever used AI-tools to perform any evidence synthesis task?

This question refers specifically to **AI evidence synthesis tools**, not to digital evidence synthesis tools in general. For example, if you have used tools such as EPPI-Reviewer, Rayyan, or LASER-AI only for manual title and abstract screening and did not use their AI functionalities?, you should answer "No"

- Yes
- No
- I am not sure

11. Is training on the use of AI to support evidence synthesis a priority for you?

- Yes
- No
- I am not sure

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Section III. Experience in using AI for evidence synthesis

12. Have you ever used AI to perform any sex and gender related task in your evidence syntheses?

- Yes
- No
- I am not sure

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Section III. Experience in using AI for evidence synthesis

13. For which sex and gender related evidence synthesis tasks you have used AI?

Select all that apply

- Topic scoping
- Formulating the review question or defining the eligibility criteria
- Designing the search strategy
- Searching for studies
- Study selection
- Data extraction
- Data synthesis, such as narrative synthesis or meta-analysis
- Certainty of evidence assessment
- Interpretation
- Report writing
- Other and I am not sure. Please specify:

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Section IV. Opportunities for AI to support the consideration of sex and gender in evidence synthesis

As a previous user of AI in evidence synthesis, we would like to hear your views on the opportunities for AI to support the consideration of sex and gender in evidence synthesis. You are invited to answer these questions regardless of whether you have incorporated sex and gender considerations in your evidence syntheses.

14. Do you think AI has the potential to improve the time efficiency of your sex and gender related tasks in evidence synthesis?

- Yes
- No
- I am not sure

15. We are interested in your views on which tasks AI could support to integrate sex and gender considerations in evidence synthesis

Please respond to what extent AI would be supportive for the following tasks (with 1 being not supportive to 5 being very supportive). Below are illustrative examples; other situations may also apply.

	1 not supportive	2	3	4	5 very supportive	I am not sure
Review planning Examples: 1. Quickly map research activities to assess to anticipate whether sex and gender are relevant for a particular review question 2. Formulate the review question and define the eligibility criteria 3. Plan and report sex and gender aspects in the review protocol	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Design the search strategies Help choosing the right search terms for sex and gender concepts, or adapt the search strategy for different databases	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Searching Examples: 1. Conduct the searches 2. Deduplicate bibliographic records 3. Obtaining full text papers 4. Support living systematic reviews and evidence maps	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Study selection Title/abstract screening or full-text assessment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Data extraction Example: extract sex and gender disaggregated data from primary studies	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Analysis Analyse or interpret results by sex and gender	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Certainty of the evidence assessment Assess whether sex and gender affect the certainty of evidence (e.g., GRADE)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reporting Reporting sex and gender aspects in the review manuscript	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reporting Generate structured summaries of sex and gender findings	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reporting Prepare a plain language summary or other dissemination products, such as blogshots	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reporting Improving AI use of full-text trial reports. For example, AI could extract sex and gender data across multiple reports linked to the same study, reducing missed information from fragmented study documentation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Other or I am not sure. Please specify:

16. Please add other opportunities not detailed above of using AI to support the consideration of sex and gender in evidence synthesis

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Section V. The challenges for AI to support the consideration of sex and gender in evidence synthesis

For each aspect below, rate how challenging it is for AI to support the consideration of sex and gender in evidence synthesis in a scale from 1 (not challenging) to 5 (very challenging). Examples are illustrative; other situations may also apply.

17. AI challenges that may apply to sex and gender in evidence synthesis

	1 not challenging	2	3	4	5 very challenging	I am not sure
Stability The AI tool may not give consistent outputs when processing the same tasks	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Hallucinations AI can produce information that is false, unsupported, or fabricated while presenting it as correct	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Transparency It is not possible to track the source behind an AI output (e.g. the model version and how it was trained)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Amplifying existing biases and lack of diversity in source data Examples: 1. Gender constructs (identity, roles, relations) are inadequately described in research so this will be replicated by AI 2. AI may be trained on datasets that do not represent sexual gender minorities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Data security / privacy It is unclear how AI deals with sensitive data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Legal issues It is unclear whether uploading articles to AI tools will have issues with copyright laws or regulations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lack of sex and gender specific evaluations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Stopping criteria in machine learning-prioritised screening There is no clear guidance on when to stop screening records, as it is uncertain when no additional relevant titles or abstracts will be found	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

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Section V. The challenges for AI to support the consideration of sex and gender in evidence synthesis

For each aspect below, rate how challenging it is for AI to support the consideration of sex and gender in evidence synthesis in a scale from 1 (not challenging) to 5 (very challenging). Examples are illustrative; other situations may also apply.

18. AI operative challenges

	1 not challenging	2	3	4	5 very challenging	I am not sure
Lack of AI skills in my team	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Choosing the adequate AI tool	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lack of specific sex and gender features in the existing digital evidence synthesis tools	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
High cost of AI tools Including regular changes of costs within short time frames	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My organization currently does not allow the use of AI in research projects Example: my IT department does not allow the use of AI	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Journals or funders may not accept evidence synthesis projects that use AI	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

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Section V. The challenges for AI to support the consideration of sex and gender in evidence synthesis

For each aspect below, rate how challenging it is for AI to support the consideration of sex and gender in evidence synthesis in a scale from 1 (not challenging) to 5 (very challenging). Examples are illustrative; other situations may also apply.

19. Existing challenges in considering sex and gender in evidence synthesis are likely to persist when using AI

	1 not challenging	2	3	4	5 very challenging	I am not sure
Lack of skills to consider sex and gender in my evidence synthesis team	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There is limited guidance on how to appropriately consider sex and gender in evidence synthesis Example: it is unclear how to handle missing sex and gender data from primary studies in evidence synthesis. Thus, AI cannot help with these sex and gender tasks	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Sex and gender data are usually absent or inconsistently reported in primary studies Example: non-binary gender data is usually not reported in trials. AI will replicate this issue	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Sex and gender data are usually reported in the supplementary materials of the article	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

20. Please add other challenges not detailed above of using AI to support the consideration of sex/gender in evidence synthesis

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Section VI. Needs for prompting on sex and gender in evidence synthesis

In generative AI (e.g., ChatGPT, Gemini), a prompt is an instruction used to guide the system and generate a specific output. Prompts may be questions, keywords or detailed instructions. One of the project aims is to develop a bank of prompts to support individuals involved in evidence synthesis in considering sex and gender. Please reply to the following questions.

21. Which sex and gender related evidence synthesis tasks would benefit most from applying reusable AI prompts?

Select maximum **four**

- Formulating the review question or defining the eligibility criteria
- Designing the search strategies
- Searching for studies
- Study selection
- Data extraction
- Data analysis
- Data synthesis
- Certainty of evidence assessment
- Interpretation of sex and gender from the discussion
- Conclusions formulation
- Manuscript writing
- Other or I am not sure. Please specify:

22. Which sex and gender related information would you want to extract from primary studies using reusable AI prompts?

Select all that apply

- Eligibility criteria
- How sex and gender were defined and operationalized in the study
- Sex and gender proportion in the recruited participants
- Participants' baseline characteristics related to sex and gender
- Study analysis plan for sex and gender
- Presentation of results by sex and gender
- Sex and gender differences in adherence or attrition
- Other or I am not sure. Please specify:

23. Which types of training on prompting for sex and gender specific data would be helpful?

Select all that apply

- Prompt engineering (the process of structuring or crafting an instruction in order to produce better outputs from a Large Language Model)
- Bias prevention, detection and mitigation (including sex and gender bias)
- Validation and quality assurance of AI outputs
- Reproducible AI workflows and documentation
- Legal, ethical or data protection considerations
- Case examples or best practices for sex and gender prompts
- Other or I am not sure. Please specify:

Section VII. Background information

24. With which gender do you identify most?

Woman

Man

Non-binary or gender diverse

Other:

I prefer not to answer

25. In which region do you currently live?

Africa

Americas

Asia

Europe

Oceania

I prefer not to answer

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Pause the survey

Survey completion

We appreciate your time in completing this survey.

Your responses to the survey have been saved.

Should you have any queries, please contact us at survey@usz.ch

Feel free to share the survey invitation with others who meet the inclusion criteria

[Artificial Intelligence \(AI\) for sex and gender analysis in evidence synthesis: survey](#)

Or copy this link: <https://befragung.usz.ch/sexgenderai/?m=A>

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Pause the survey